

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: GERMANY

Research for the future of our freshwaters

Angelina Tittmann

Head of Communications and Knowledge Transfer
Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries
Berlin Germany
Email: tittmann@igb-berlin.de

Whether as a resource, recreational space or biodiversity hotspot: inland waters are the focus of research conducted at the Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries, or IGB for short. Intact waters are indispensable for human well-being and the conservation of a fascinating fauna and flora. However, rivers, lakes, floodplains and wetlands are among the habitats most affected by human activity – with massive negative impacts on their biodiversity. Climate and landscape changes are further increasing the pressure on inland waters. Counteracting this requires a sustainable approach to manage freshwater resources and ecosystems. Cooperation between different disciplines, involving user groups and affected stakeholders, is essential for this. This is what IGB stands for. As Germany's largest and one of the leading international research centres for freshwaters, scientists from all over the world study the structures and processes in rivers, lakes and wetlands as well as their populations, communities and ecosystems. While this basic research is certainly well known to limnologists worldwide, IGB also conducts applied research. A few examples of recent projects are elucidated here.

Spatio-temporal dynamics of water-based recreational activities

The AQUATAG project, for example, is investigating when and where inland waters are used particularly intensively for recreational activities, and how this recreational use could be better managed. After all, recreational use and the quality of water bodies influence each other. For example, each type of use has its own demands on the quality of a lake or a river, such as natural environment, infrastructure, accessibility and visitor density. The project team follows the key assumption that quality of use and ecological quality can be addressed via the common interface "ecological and social carrying capacity". The mandatory basis for this is the systematic, temporally and spatially differentiated recording of the various uses and effects. To this end, researchers are bringing together novel research approaches and data sources at different spatial and temporal levels. For example, they combine data from GIS-analysis, surveys, field studies and social media by evaluating geo-referenced data from Twitter and fitness trackers, and compare it with user information from various sports and leisure associations. As the project exemplifies, the relatively young research branch of recreation ecology holds ample potential for research into aquatic systems, e.g. for species monitoring or for work on ecosystem status and, as here, human impacts and well-being.

Find out more: <https://www.igb-berlin.de/en/projekt/aquatag>

Services to human society provided by ecosystems of rivers and their floodplains

Recreation, flood retention and carbon sequestration are just some examples of the diverse ecosystem services that freshwaters provide to society. A cooling effect during heat waves, purification and provisioning of water resources, habitat diversity and fishery yields could also be mentioned here.

Photo by Sächsisches Landesamt für Umwelt, Landwirtschaft und Geologie

Employees of the predecessor institution IfB during field work in 1955. The origins of IGB can be traced even further back to 1893, when hydrobiologist Johannes Frenzel founded the Biological and Fishery Experimental Station at Müggelsee – one of the first research facilities in this field.

Photo by Dmytrenko Vlad, shutterstock

Today, enormous quantities of photos, videos and texts of all kinds are posted on the internet. More and more people use fitness trackers and post their data online, while spending their leisure time at inland waters. For a few years, scientists have been taking advantage of big data on the internet.

What all these ecosystem services have in common is that they can only be guaranteed in the long term if rivers and lakes are in good ecological status. But maintaining and restoring surface waters and floodplains is often a complex and expensive undertaking. Sometimes it is even uncertain which measures are worthwhile, because restoration goals also depend to some extent on the different views of stakeholders. Together with partners from water management authorities, scientists at IGB have therefore developed an assessment approach based on the concept of ecosystem services that enables them to show and quantify the various benefits of rivers and floodplains to various parts of society. The River

Ecosystem Service Index (RESI) developed at IGB facilitates the identification of optimised management scenarios that support most sustainable management goals and uses. Integration of such analyses into planning procedures may help practitioners to identify and defuse potential conflicts of use at an early stage. To this end, RESI has already been applied to an 80-km section of the Danube River, where it facilitated the reconciliation of flood retention and nature conservation goals in regional planning.

Find out more:

<https://www.igb-berlin.de/en/project/resi>

<https://www.igb-berlin.de/en/project/ides>

Species protection through environmentally friendly lighting

A relatively new but rapidly increasing stressor for aquatic ecosystems and their biotic communities is excessive artificial light at night. IGB has pioneered the young research field of light pollution, bringing together different scientific disciplines and citizen scientists. As a result of this engagement, there is now a deeper understanding of why light is one reason for the decline in insect numbers worldwide, and how artificial light affects the hormonal balance and natural behaviour of fish and other vertebrates. But solutions are also being developed: In the current AuBe project, IGB researchers are developing insect-friendly street lighting designs together with partners from the lighting technology sector. These are intended to counteract the progressive loss of insect biomass and the rapidly increasing illumination of night landscapes and habitats.

Find out more:

<https://www.igb-berlin.de/en/projekt/species-protection-through-environmental-friendly-lighting-aube>

Waters and fisheries sciences since the 19th century

Research at IGB not only pursues promising new approaches, it also reaches far back into history: Research on fish biology was conducted at one of its precursor institutions as early as the late 19th century: the Biological and Fishery Experimental Station at Lake Müggelsee. A few years later, this station became the "Royal Institute for Inland Fisheries" and, after World War II in 1951, the "Institute for Fisheries". In 1992, this institute and two other predecessor research institutions were merged to create IGB. At that time, IGB employed 103 scientists; it now employs a total of about 250 people, including around 150 scientists. A nationally and internationally acknowledged aquatic research institute soon developed, combining expertise from hydrology, biogeochemistry, physics, microbiology, ecology, evolutionary ecology, fish ecology and fisheries biology under one roof. Disciplinary research is bundled in five research departments. In addition, programme areas address issues of high social and scientific relevance, such as global change, aquatic biodiversity and sustainable use and management of freshwaters. The numerous research activities involve societal stakeholders and are carried out in close cooperation with universities and research institutions, both locally and worldwide. The institute is still located on the shores of Berlin's Lake Müggelsee, with an additional location at Lake Stechlin, Brandenburg's most famous clear-water lake.

Would you like to learn more about IGB? The bimonthly FRESHWATERS NEWS keeps you up to date with the latest research findings of the institute and its cooperation partners > www.igb-berlin.de/en/newsletter

<https://www.igb-berlin.de/en>

<https://twitter.com/LeibnizIGB>

Photo by Joachim Pressl on Unsplash

Inland waters are particularly affected by light pollution as the shores of rivers and lakes are often densely built up and brightly lit at night. After all, many flying insects are drawn to light sources, where they perish, leading to a decline in their natural habitat. New research results at IGB show that this effect is also applicable under water. Researchers say that current researchers, current strategies for reducing the impact of light pollution do not go far enough in protecting aquatic insect species effectively.

Photo by Fatseyeva, Shutterstock

Using the example of the multi-state Danube River, IGB researchers assessed different ecosystem services for the current status quo of the river and its floodplains as well as for two different planning states.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5729999>